

Publication of FAIR Data and Metadata

Part 0: Introduction

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Reiner Lemoine Institut

- Not-for-profit research institute
- 100 % subsidiary of Reiner Lemoine Foundation (RLS)
- Established 2010 in Berlin
- Managing Director: Dr. Kathrin Goldammer

Objective

Applied Research for 100% Renewable Energies

Scientific staff

~ 60 researchers and 40 students in 3 research fields

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Transformation of Energy Systems

Energy System Analysis

- Energy scenarios
- Sector coupling: electricity, heat, mobility
- Expansion scenarios

Power Grids

- Storage positioning
- Flexibility assessment
- Distribution grids

Data Management & Open Science

- Research Data Management
- Databases
- Data Processing
- Ontology and Knowledge Graphs

Visualisation & Participation

- Interactive maps & Tools
- Web interfaces
- Participation

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Open Science - Energy System Modelling

„Open data, open source, and open access in relation to the energy modelling process.“
[Pfenninger et al. \(2018\)](#) licensed [CC BY 4.0](#)

Open Energy Family

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OEP

openenergy-platform.org

- University Magdeburg (OvGU) is host and main developer
- Funded projects until 2028
- Server deployment for +10 years guaranteed by OvGU
- Cross-tier community project
- Code available at [GitHub](#)

Gefördert durch:

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

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FAIR Principles

	DE_BadenWue	DE_Bayern	DE_Berlin		
DE_Brandenburg					
processHeat500	t0001	0.000087	0.000076	0.00007	0.00007
processHeat500	t0002	0.000085	0.000076	0.000068	0.000068
processHeat500	t0003	0.000086	0.000076	0.000069	0.000069
processHeat500	t0004	0.000087	0.000077	0.00007	0.00007
processHeat500	t0005	0.000121	0.000116	0.000112	0.000112
processHeat500	t0006	0.000167	0.000168	0.00017	0.00017
processHeat500	t0007	0.000195	0.000199	0.000203	0.000203
processHeat500	t0008	0.000204	0.000208	0.000212	0.000212
processHeat500	t0009	0.000205	0.000209	0.000212	0.000212
processHeat500	t0010	0.000188	0.00019	0.000191	0.000191
processHeat500	t0011	0.000187	0.000188	0.000189	0.000189
processHeat500	t0012	0.000184	0.000187	0.000187	0.000187
processHeat500	t0013	0.000182	0.000184	0.000186	0.000186
processHeat500	t0014	0.000181	0.000183	0.000185	0.000185

- ▶ **Findable:** Data and Metadata should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of data sets and services
- ▶ **Accessible:** Once the user finds the required data, she/he needs to know how they can be accessed
- ▶ **Interoperable:** The data needs to be integrated with other data. In addition the need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage and processing
- ▶ **Reusable:** The goal is to optimize the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings

<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

„The opposite of ‘open’ isn’t ‘closed’. The opposite of ‘open’ is ‘broken’.“

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